

Research on Medicinal Plant Resources in Cham Chu Nature Reserve, Yen Thuan Commune, Ham Yen District, Tuyen Quang Province

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Abstract

Our investigation has documented 400 medicinal plant species belonging to 309 genera and 117 families across five divisions of vascular plants. The life form composition of plants in the study area comprises five groups. The group with the least number of species is the chamaephytes, with 27 species (6.75%), followed by the therophytes with 35 species (8.75%), cryptophytes with 41 species (10.25%), hemicryptophytes with 45 species (11.25%), and the phanerophytes with the highest number of species at 252 (63.00%). The geographical elements have been determined for 390 species (97.50%), while 10 species (2.50%) remain undetermined. In the study area, 18 medicinal plant species (4.5%) have been identified as threatened and in need of conservation. Among these, 15 species (83.33%) require protection according to the Vietnam Red Book; 5 species (27.78%) are listed under Government Decree 06/2019/NĐ-CP; and 5 species (27.78%) are listed in the 2007 Vietnam Red List of Medicinal Plants. Currently, the medicinal plant resources in the study area are being exploited by local inhabitants and are at risk of depletion if conservation policies and measures are not implemented.

Keywords: Resources, Medicinal Plants, Cham Chu, Yen Thuan.

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Introduction

Tuyen Quang has a natural area of 586,790 hectares and is located in the midland and northern mountainous region of Vietnam. The province's natural conditions are quite favorable for enhancing the biological productivity of both natural and artificial ecosystems. Therefore, a primary task for Tuyen Quang is to research and evaluate biodiversity in general and the flora in particular, to develop strategies for conservation and sustainable development.

Ham Yen District in Tuyen Quang Province comprises 18 administrative units, including one town and 17 communes. The district covers a total area of 90,055 hectares, with 21,810 hectares of agricultural land, 62,291 hectares of forestry land, 1,930 hectares of specialized land, and 1,112 hectares of residential land. Yen Thuan Commune is one of the communes in Ham Yen District, characterized by its location in the upper region of the district, 40 km north of the district center. The terrain is complex, primarily consisting of steep rocky mountains and many streams. Geographically, it borders Trung Ha Commune of Chiem Hoa District to the east, Vinh Hao Commune of Bac Quang District, Ha Giang Province to

the west, Bach Xa and Minh Khuong Communes to the south, and Vo Diem Commune of Bac Quang District, Ha Giang Province to the north.

Yen Thuan Commune has a total natural area of 7,495.84 hectares, including 7,202.58 hectares of agricultural land, 280.48 hectares of non-agricultural land, and 12.78 hectares of unused land. The main ethnic groups living together in the commune are the Tay, Dao, Kinh, H'Mong, and several other ethnicities. The commune has 14 hamlets with a total of 1,388 households, corresponding to 5,915 people, of which the ethnic minority population accounts for over 80% of the total population. Currently, Yen Thuan Commune is classified as a category III area, with 11 out of 14 hamlets designated as especially difficult, accounting for 78.57% according to Decision No. 612/QĐ-UBND dated September 16, 2021, of the Committee for Ethnic Minority Affairs. The commune has 321 poor households (23.13%) and 288 near-poor households (20.75%). The living conditions of ethnic minorities are still challenging, especially in hamlets far from the commune center. Despite significant investments in infrastructure, there is still a lack of comprehensive and synchronized development. The economy is primarily focused on agricultural and forestry production, with limited application of scientific and technical advancements in agriculture. The local population has not yet fully leveraged the potential and strengths of the area to develop the economy and improve living standards, and employment remains seasonal, affecting income.

Subjects and Research Methods

Subjects

The research subjects are medicinal plant resources in the Cham Chu Nature Reserve, located in Yen Thuan Commune, Ham Yen District, Tuyen Quang Province. The research period extends from August 2023 to June 2024.

Research Methods

Inheritance Method

Relevant documents and reports on the flora of the study area by scientists and authorities were selectively collected and inherited.

Botanical Research Method

The botanical research method employed in this study follows the methodologies of Hoang Chung (2008) and Nguyen Nghia Thin (2007).

Transect Surveys

Based on the area map, contour lines were identified, and transects perpendicular to these contour lines were then determined, crossing various plant communities. The distance between transects ranged from 50-100 meters, varying according to the terrain and vegetation cover. The observation width was 2 meters for shrub and forest vegetation, and 1 meter for grassland vegetation.

Standard Plots

For forest vegetation, the standard plot area (SPA) was 400m² (20m x 20m); for shrub vegetation, it was 16m² (4m x 4m); and for grassland vegetation, it was 1m² (1m x 1m). The SPAs were located in representative and characteristic plant communities. In the forest vegetation, board plots (BP) of 16m² (4m x 4m) were established.

Data Analysis and Processing Methods

- The method of Nguyen Nghia Thin (2007) was used for processing plant samples.

- The following references were used for species identification and morphological comparison: "Names of Vietnam's Forest Plants" by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, 2000; "Plants of Vietnam" by Pham Hoang Ho, 1991-1993; "List of Plant Species of Vietnam" by Nguyen Tien Ban and colleagues, 2003, 2005.

- Additional references included works by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (2000), Pham Hoang Ho (1991-1993), Nguyen Tien Ban and colleagues (2003, 2005), Tran Dinh Ly (1993), Vo Van Chi (1997), La Dinh Moi and colleagues (2001-2002), and the "Institute of Ecology and Biological Resources" for determining the utilitarian value of plant species.

- The plant list was arranged according to the evolutionary system of divisions, with scientific names sorted alphabetically in Latin. The method of Nguyen Nghia Thin (2007) was used to evaluate the diversity of taxa within divisions, classes, families, and genera. Plant life forms were identified according to Raunkiaer (1934), and geographical elements were determined following Nguyen Nghia Thin (2004). Threatened species were identified according to the "Vietnam Red Book, 2007"; Government Decree 06/2019/NĐ-CP; the "Vietnam Red List of Medicinal Plants"; and the "Handbook of Medicinal Plants Needing Conservation in Vietnam" by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN). Microsoft Excel software was also used for data processing.

Survey and Interview Method

Interviews were conducted following the method of Nguyen Nghia Thin (2007) with scientists, experts, managers, and local community members. The results were then synthesized, analyzed, and used to propose conservation solutions.

Research Results

Diversity of Medicinal Plant Species Composition

The study recorded 400 species of medicinal plants, belonging to 309 genera and 117 families (Table 1). The division Magnoliophyta (flowering plants) has the highest proportion, with 371 species (92.75%), 287 genera (86.32%), and 101 families (86.32%). This is followed by the division Polypodiophyta (ferns) with 19 species (4.75%), 15 genera (4.85%), and 10 families (8.55%). The remaining divisions have lower proportions: Lycopodiophyta (club mosses) with 4 species (1%), 2 genera (0.65%), and 2 families (1.71%); Pinophyta (conifers) with 4 species (1%), 4 genera (1.29%), and 3 families (2.56%); and Equisetophyta (horsetails) with 2 species (0.5%), 1 genus (0.32%), and 1 family (0.85%).

Table 1. Distribution of Medicinal Plant Taxa within Divisions in the Cham Chu Nature Reserve, Yen Thuan Commune, Ham Yen District, Tuyen Quang Province

No.	Scientific Name	Number of Species	Ratio	Number of Genera	Ratio	Number of Families	Ratio
1	Lycopodiophyta	4	1,00	2	0,65	2	1,71
2	Euisetophyta	2	0,50	1	0,32	1	0,85
3	Polypodiophyta	19	4,75	15	4,85	10	8,55
4	Pinophyta	4	1,00	4	1,29	3	2,56
5	Magnoliophyta	371	92,75	287	92,88	101	86,32
Total		400	100	309	100	117	100

Diversity in Life Form Composition of Medicinal Plants

The life form composition of medicinal plants is categorized into 5 groups (Table 2): Ground-hugging

shrubs with the least number at 27 species (6.75%), followed by annual herbs at 35 species (8.75%), hidden shrubs at 41 species (10.25%), semi-hidden shrubs at 45 species (11.25%), and finally, tall shrubs with the highest number at 252 species (63.00%). From this, the life form spectrum of medicinal plants is formulated as: SB = 63.00 Tr + 6.75 Ch + 11.25 Sc + 10.25 Ph + 8.75 An. It is evident that among medicinal plants, the tall shrub group represents the highest proportion.

Table 2. Quantity and Percentage (%) of Life Form Groups of Medicinal Plants in the Cham Chu Nature Reserve, Yen Thuan Commune, Ham Yen District, Tuyen Quang Province

No.	Lifeform Group	Taxon	Number of Species	ratio (%)
1	Phanerophytes	Ph	252	63,00
2	Chamaephytes	Ch	27	6,75
3	Hemicryptophytes	He	45	11,25
4	Cryptophytes	Cr	41	10,25
5	Therophytes	Th	35	8,75
Total			400	100

Geographical Diversity of Medicinal Plants

The research results (Table 3) show that of the 400 medicinal plant species identified, the geographical factors of 390 species (97.50%) have been determined, while 10 species (2.50%) remain unidentified. The factor with the highest proportion is the Asian Tropical group, with 281 species (70.25%), followed by the Paleotropical group with 27 species (6.75%). The remaining groups, including Pantropical, Temperate, Endemic to Vietnam, and Cultivated species, account for 2% to 5.5% respectively. Within the Asian Tropical group, there are 5 distinct geographical factors arranged in descending order: Indochina-Malesia with 112 species (28%), Asian Tropical with 66 species (16.50%), Mainland Southeast Asia with 62 species (15.5%), Indochina-South China with 28 species (7%), and Indochina-India with 13 species (3.25%). Thus, the dominant geographical factor of the medicinal flora is the Indochina-Malesia region within the Asian Tropical group, which is consistent with the geographical factors of the vegetation in the studied area.

Table 3. Geographical Factors of Medicinal Plants in the Cham Chu Nature Reserve, Yen Thuan Commune, Ham Yen District, Tuyen Quang Province

Stt	Geographical Factors	Number of Species	Ratio (%)
1	Global Factors	11	2.75
2	Pantropical	22	5.50
3	Paleotropical	27	6.75
4	Asian Tropical	281	70.25
5	Temperate	22	5.50
6	Endemic to Vietnam	19	4.75
7	Cultivated Species	8	2.00
8	Unidentified Geographical Factors	10	2.50
9	Identified Geographical Factors	390	97.50

Diversity of Conservation Value of Medicinal Plants

The research results show that 18 species of medicinal plants (41.86%) are at risk of being threatened and require conservation. The results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Statistics of Medicinal Plant Species Requiring Conservation in Cham Chu Nature Reserve, Yen Thuan commune, Ham Yen district, Tuyen Quang Province

TT	Vietnamese name/ Scientific name	conservation status		
		Vietnam Red Book	Government Decree 06	Medicinal Plant Red List
1	Ba kích (<i>Morinda officinalis</i>)			EN
2	Bách bộ đá (<i>Stemona saxorum</i>).	VU		
3	Cốt toái bồ (<i>Drynaria fortunei</i>)	EN		EN
4	Củ bình vôi (<i>Stephania rotunda</i>)		IIA	
5	Củ dôm (<i>Stephania dielsiana</i>)	VU	IIA	EN
6	Đại kế (<i>Cirsium japonicum</i>)	VU		
7	Hà thủ ô đỏ (<i>Fallopia multiflora</i>)	VU		EN
8	Hèo sợi to (<i>Guibania grossefibrosa</i>)	EN		
9	Hoa tiên (<i>Asarum glabrum</i>)	VU	IIA	
10	Hoàng đằng (<i>Fibraurea tinctoria</i>)		IIA	
11	Kim tuyến tơ (<i>Anoectochilus setaceus</i>)	EN	IA	
12	Lá khô (<i>Ardisia sivestris</i>)	VU		VU
13	Lát hoa (<i>Chukrasia tabularis</i>)	VU		
14	Lộc vừng (<i>Barringtonia asiatica</i>)	VU		
15	Ngũ gia bì gai (<i>Acanthopanax trifoliatum</i>)	EN		
16	Ngũ gia bì hương (<i>Acanthopanax gracilistylus</i>)	EN		
17	Rau sắng (<i>Melientha suavis</i>)	VU		
18	Trầm hương (<i>Aquilaria crassna</i>)	EN		

According to the Vietnam Red Book, 15 species (83.33%) require protection, with 6 species (33.33%) assessed as Endangered (EN) and 9 species (50%) as Vulnerable (VN). According to Government Decree 06/2019/ND-CP, 5 species (27.78%) require protection. The assessment includes 1 species (5.56%) listed as Strictly Prohibited for commercial exploitation and use (IA), and 4 species (22.22%) listed as Restricted for commercial exploitation and use (IIA). According to the 2007 Vietnam Red List of Medicinal Plants, 5 species (27.78%) require protection, with 4 species (22.22%) assessed as Endangered (EN) and 1 species (5.56%) as Vulnerable (VN). According to the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN 2000), there are no listed species.

Conclusion

Our survey results have documented 400 medicinal plant species belonging to 309 genera and 117 families across 5 major vascular plant phyla. The life form composition of the plant community in the study area comprises 5 major life form groups. The group with the lowest number of species is the herbaceous rosette plants with 27 species (6.75%), followed by annual herbs with 35 species (8.75%), rhizomatous herbs with 41 species (10.25%), hemicryptophytes with 45 species (11.25%), and the dominant group of phanerophytes (terrestrial woody plants) with 252 species (63.00%). The geographic affinities were determined for 390 species (97.50%), with the remaining 10 species (2.50%) unidentified. The group with the highest representation is the Asian tropical element with 281 species (70.25%), followed by the Paleotropical element with 27 species (6.75%), while the remaining groups, including Pantropical, Temperate, Endemic to Vietnam, and Cultivated species, range from 2% to 5.5%. Within the study area, 18 medicinal plant species (4.5%) have been identified as facing threats and requiring conservation efforts. Of these, 15 species (83.33%) are listed in the Vietnam Red Book as requiring protection, 5 species (27.78%) are listed in Government Decree 06/2019/ND-CP, 5 species (27.78%) are listed in the 2007 Vietnam Red List of Medicinal Plants, and none are listed by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN 2000).

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